

Introduction to Engineering Design

Chapter 8

Design Tools & Technologies

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Learning Objectives to be achieved:

1. To recognize the various design tools used in Engineering Design
2. To familiarize with the different design technologies that can be used in Engineering Design

7.0 Introduction

This eighth week's topics are the third-course objectives, which state, "Differentiate between the application of technologies to small-scale engineering projects in developing and developed societies."

The seventh week's topics respond to the fourth-course objective states, "Develop a conceptual design with the material specification based on broad design parameters including cost and sustainability". The design concept used in this class is based on axiomatic design.

The sixth-week topic aims to help the engineering designer to grasp the ability to search for information and use it to identify the gaps and create a new idea.

The fifth-week topics correspond to the fourth-course objectives, which state, "Develop a conceptual design with the material specification based on broad design parameters including cost and sustainability".

The fourth week's topics respond to the first-course objective, "To identify and apply the various phases and processes within an engineering design process".

The third week's topics discuss communication, collaboration and team success, even in a diverse team membership or multi-disciplinary nature.

The second week's response to the second-course objective states, "On completion of this subject, the students can participate within and contribute to a multi-discipline engineering design team through the application of team roles and communication". It also

In the first week's discussion, the challenge to take part in the Sustainable Development Goals action using the Greening Engineering Framework (GEF) that served as a theme to the Engineering

Design Challenge 2022, was taken on board as an engineering design team is discussed and organized in the second week.

7.1 Design tools used in Engineering Design

The advancement in digital technology creates life works easy and all aspects of life have moved along with it, even in design using design tools. Design tools are computer software and programs used to create new designs like painting, sketching, drawing, 3D modelling, perspective drawing, graphic design, etc. A sketch is a 2D profile or cross-section and is the basis for most 3D models. Creating a model usually begins with a sketch. From the sketch, the features of a product are shown. Combining one or more elements make a part and combining the right pieces to create an assembly. A drawing of an object is created from the parts or assemblies.

Below are the few tools that can are used in Engineering Design class that a newbie can work on :

7.1.1 SketchUp

It is an online free 3D design software launched in 2000, ranked as one of the best CAD software due to its powerful 2D and 3D modelling tools. It's the easiest program to create three-dimensional models of buildings, furniture, and everyday objects. And second, you can get your hands on a handy copy for free.

The toolbar with all the basic and advanced tools is on the dashboard's right side, while the drawing and navigational tools are on the left side. The design can be manipulated in any way you want using specific tools and features.

Key Features

- ✓ Mobile application - The SketchUp mobile application views the 3D models on your mobile, thus giving the user ability to work even while travelling.
- ✓ Cloud storage - SketchUp understands that every design created is a piece of art and provides the user with 10 GB of Trimble connect cloud storage. The storage space can be shared with teams for collaborative work.
- ✓ Interoperability - Work can be imported in multiple file types like SKP, JPG, PNG etc. You can also export files in various types.

User Interface

- ✓ SketchUp 3D design software will take time to understand its functionalities, but numerous online guides and tutorials are available online.

Best For

- ✓ SketchUp is an appropriate 3D modeling software for anyone with almost the basic features can be unlocked with the free plan. However, subscription plans are available for some advanced features and storage options.

With the free version, you can design complex 3-D models and print pictures and export 2-D art to use in websites or other programs. The model can be saved as a JPEG or PNG file and can be edited in Photoshop. Can also save the models in the .kmz file format that place models in Google Earth.

Here's the lowdown on the file formats that is created with SketchUp:

- Standard 3-D file format: .skp. You can also save to formats used by earlier versions of SketchUp.
- Google Earth: .kmz. Place your models anywhere on the planet!
- 2-D image files: JPEG (.jpg), Portable Network Graphics (.png), Tagged Image File (.tif), Windows Bitmap (.bmp). You can both import and export images in all of these formats and also import Targa files (.tga).
- 3-D models: SketchUp (.skp); Google Earth terrain, 3DS (.3ds); AutoCAD (.dwg, .dxf); DEM (.dem, .ddf). You can import models created in these formats and export your models as SketchUp (.skp) or Google Earth (.kmz).
- Animations and walk-throughs. Video for Windows (.avi); QuickTime (.mov) files on Mac.

Steps on the Windows version of SketchUp

1. Choose View → Toolbars → Large Tool Set. A new toolbar appears with buttons running vertically down the left side of the window. This new toolbar includes all the tools in the Getting Started toolbar, so in the next step, hide the Getting Started toolbar. Initially, the large toolbar is attached to the drawing area, but by clicking the bar at the top, can drag it away from the drawing area to create a floating toolbar.
2. Choose View → Toolbars → Getting Started. Before you click, checkmarks are next to both the Large Tool Set and the Getting Started options. In the View menu, a checkmark indicates that an option is visible in your workspace. Clicking a checked item hides it from view and removes the checkmark.
3. Choose View → Toolbars → Standard. The Standard toolbar provides the tools to find in almost every program, though the buttons look slightly different. These buttons let the user create, open, and save SketchUp files. You also see Cut, Copy, Paste, and Erase buttons. In the next group, you see Undo and Redo arrows. Bringing up the rear is a Print button. Last but certainly not least is a button that's unique to SketchUp. The blue circle with the letter i is the Model Info button, which provides juicy tidbits about the model you're building.
4. Choose View → Toolbars → Views. When you work in 3-D, you change views frequently, or you move the camera from the "SketchUp think" perspective. For example, suppose you want to ensure your model fits together properly. Sometimes the only way

to see whether a gap exists between two objects is to view them from a different angle. The six view buttons get a lot of use. The Camera Standard Views buttons are Iso (short for isometric or angled view), Top, Front, Right, Back, and Left.

5. To add one final toolbar, choose View → Toolbars → Face Style. The six buttons on the Face Style toolbar change how SketchUp objects appear in the drawing area. For example, the X-ray button makes object surfaces semitransparent—which helps work with complex models. The other face styles are wireframe, hidden line, shaded, shaded with textures, and monochrome.

7.1.2 AutoCAD

AutoCAD is a computer-aided design (CAD) software for architects, engineers, and construction professionals who rely on to create precise 2D and 3D drawings. With AutoCAD, users can draft and edit 2D geometry and 3D models with solids, surfaces, and mesh objects; annotate drawings with text, dimensions, leaders, and tables; and customize with add-on apps and APIs.

Key Features (Learn about AutoCAD An Introduction to AutoCAD for Beginners)

- Creates users produce quality designs in less time with significant improvements.
- Has new stunning visual experience, enhanced documentation, and new design features.
- It enables increased connectivity and customizations that allow users to share designs and customize the user interface.
- High-Fidelity lines and curves
- Coordination model
- Point cloud dynamic
- UCS Point cloud geometry extraction
- Smart dimensioning
- Revision cloud enhancements
- PDF enhancements
- Optimized PDF output
- Searchable text in exported PDFs
- Hyperlink support in exported PDFs
- Amplified powerful rendering
- Customization of the user interface

7.1.3 SolidWorks

SolidWorks published by Dassault Systèmes is a solid modelling computer-aided design (CAD) and computer-aided engineering application. (Solidworks).

Key features (Solidworks):

- It demonstrate the operation of your design under real-world conditions

- Simulate and analyze design performance
- Product Data Management (PDM) solutions

7.1.4 Others

PTC Creo

Creo is developed by PTC, is a Computer-aided design (CAD) apps that supports product design for discrete manufacturers. The suite comprises apps that is delivering a distinct set of user capabilities role within product development (PTC Creo). PTC Creo product design software follows the parametric modelling approach. That means the software utilizes parameters, dimensions, features, and relationships to capture intended product behaviour so that future automation and optimization for that product is possible as the project progresses. Creo runs on Microsoft Windows and is part of a suite of collaborative applications that address each step of the product development process. Design engineers use Creo to create complete 3D digital models of products, with data that can be used downstream in analysis, prototyping, tooling design, and manufacturing.

Creo allows students to work with state-of-the-art 3D CAD software and enabling them to take ideas and concepts to create a products. Through Creo one can become an Engineer of the Future. It is the best tool ion design, analysis and simulation tools directly in the hands of the students.

7.2 Design technologies role in Engineering Design

The design engineer may utilize two-dimensional or three-dimensional representations of objects whose representation choice depends on the intended viewer of the information. For communicating with non-engineering professionals, common three-dimensional drawings, called pictorials, such as perspectives and isometric representations, are performed. These drawings offer a representation that is more like what one would see with their own eyes but can be deceptive in terms of accurate dimensions. These drawings contain little information about construction or manufacturing techniques. Engineering professionals often create a three-dimensional solid model with two-dimensional views showing orthographic projections, section views, and auxiliary views to describe actual unit dimensions, tolerances, and materials. Engineers also use simulations and virtual reality representations to depict, simulate, and interact with objects prior to their manufacture or construction, thus avoiding costly mistakes in fabrication.

The technologies allows:

- Design Engineers are critical users of technologies
- Designers and producers of designed solutions
- Through these technologies design engineers can investigate. They can Develop and critique designed sustainable futures

- Use design and systems thinking to create ethical innovative design ideas
- Them to communicate these innovative design ideas to a range of audiences
- Them to create designed solutions for a range of suitable contexts by creatively choosing and safely manipulating various materials, components, systems, tools and equipment
- Them to be able to transfer the knowledge and skills gained from design and technologies to new situations
- Them to understand the roles and responsibilities of people in design and technology occupations and how they contribute to society.

References

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